
RE: “Do we really have to have a [insert type] of war?”
→ War is the anti-MIMS, and yet it exists.

MESS 0010

MIMS 2.81 - Violence as a MIMS

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ABSTRACT

In “Boxing out Hyper-Masculinity” the author laid out some pre-MIMS ideas surrounding understanding the catastrophes and EPEMC’s role in helping society to avoid the continuity of masculine violence, and machismo (for lack of a better word.) In the progression of this hope, or plan, the author now makes the case that the proper use of the teaching of violence, and of the control of one’s power is **absolutely key** to the achievement of mimsical progress (futuraization). Moreover this progress makes an individual or a society/culture (larger structure) healthier and improved, as well. The author projects that the understanding of Shi will improve all of STEMM, especially medicine, and eventually lead to more civil society. Violent, but controlled, rather than the bad results created when pacifism reigns the idea-sphere.

Keywords: Violence - MIMS - STEMM - Kung Fu - Shaolin - Buddhism - Karate Kid - Domestic - Bullies

Dear Readers,

I truly do believe that Government is the worst MIMS¹ ever created². Some might think it is money, or the Federal Reserve System³, or capitalism, but I think that is all very besides the point. The American Founding Fathers made a wise observation which led to a wonderful MIMS: the Constitution and the Bill of Rights; which means that government is an unfortunately necessary evil, and it can only be tolerable if minimal. Nevertheless, war is definitely the quintessential anti-MIMS. No one wins a war, they only achieve a temporary stay of victory, and temporary peace, and this peace is maintained through a sort of “royal sway” or hegemonic Shi⁴ (force field of power and position), which pushes upon the inalienable rights of others in a demonstration of power. It does not establish a classically liberal equality, fraternity, and justice!

Nevertheless, when we look - with EPEMC⁵ - into the mythohistory and geological, biological, and electric versions of those for evidence, we see that linguistics, writing, weaponry/war, and government are all intertwined with a) plasmaglyphics/scripts from Perattian formations seen during Velikovsky’s “Ages in Chaos,” and b) thunderbolt related symbology and meaning (eg. hammer, lightning, thunder, earthquake, etc.). These motifs and archetypes **cannot be ignored** and have a concrete and definite form from hieroglyphics, Chinese scripts, earthworks, cave and rock art, OOPArts⁶, UNESCO sites, you name it. They are more definite than the entire field of paleontology, which amounts to >90% artwork from what the author can gather.

So, if violence was seen in the sky and this informed mankind, and if mimsically speaking violence has been taught to man (consider David vs. Goliath⁷, or the Fantasia Dinosaur sequence, etc.) because violence has a definite meaning and shape within the real Universe (as parasitism does in biology)... then can it be a MIMS? That is to say, can violence act as a MIMS where war is an anti-MIMS? The short answer is **absolutely and unequivocally yes.** I will show you several examples.

Wax On, Wax Off

The history of martial arts is far too broad to utilize it all. We shall stick to the mimsy of Chinese “gong fu” and to a lesser extent Japanese Budo, particularly Karate, which is really a southern White Crane gongfu derivative⁸.

The history goes, legends say, back to the arrival of Bodhidharma at the Shaolin Temple, circa 495 AD⁹. The fact is that this is probably wrong, and the context for why he is there is in dispute, and it may involve racism against the Indian Yogi. Nevertheless, after his struggles to attain control of the temple, Daruma is said to have brought Ch’an (Zen) Buddhism, along with 4 sutras (memorized, for he crossed the Himalayas by foot with a stick and bowl and robe only). He found the monks couldn’t stay awake for 20 hours of dhyana practice, so he beat them and established the I-Chin-Ching¹⁰ yogic exercises. This led to roughhousing, and then to fighting, and finally to self-defense. Later, in a more definite era, the temple was crucial in a battle, with 13 legendary monks fighting with great prowess and strength, and “saving the day.”

¹ Membranous Interface of Material and Spiritual

² https://www.academia.edu/62757621/Conquering_the_Solar_System

³ Or the Greatest (in terms of influence) invention of history, or at least neck and neck with the light bulb: fractional reserve lending fiat.

⁴ https://www.academia.edu/50357891/MIMS_and_Shi

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/36753648/Extended_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Cosmology_EPEMC

⁶ <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl> pp.10-22

⁷ 1 Samuel 17:1-25:7

⁸ [KUNG FU QUEST 2- WHITE CRANE BOXING EP 5 \(ENG SUB\)](#)

⁹ [Bodhidharma: Founder of Zen, from India to Shaolin](#) & [The Legendary Bodhidharma](#)

¹⁰ <https://www.amazon.com/Chin-Ching-Exercises-Strength-Flexibility/dp/0991435508>

The long and short of it is that violence occurred in 5 stages, each with a direct mimsical outcome:

1. Self-violence of Daruma in his discipline, including cutting off his eyelids. This led to the strenuous formulation of Zen meditation, which is good because in Japan the sutras were dumped, and for the most part Zen became the koanic musings of idle drunkards, and was far removed from this origin by the illustrious Bodhidharma (POS theory¹¹ in action... degradation of the original by less than worthy mendicants or moochers, who made a mystique out of the concrete, as per Ayn Rand's suggestion).
2. Self-violence by Hui Ke, in removing his own arm¹²; this established the ideal of the dedicated student... it was later repeated in the reformation era of Taoism with the creation of Quanzhen Taoism¹³, whose first adherents were so strict they even got divorced rather than face the wrath of the assiduous teachers.
3. Violence upon the students with beatings to force practices to achieve health and meditation. This led to the establishment of a Chinese cultural ideal of dealing with vagrants and useless ne'er-do-wells, and sadly children. However, it has done them good stead as seen in the 2008 opening of the Olympics, and the hard work that is still done to this day at Shaolin Temple doing kung fu is shown off in the "Wheel of Life" show¹⁴, and in myriad movies, including Gordon Liu's "36 Chambers of Shaolin" and in the TV show "Kung Fu." It helped for Bruce Lee to win over an entire world to his way of thinking, and his martyrdom (spiritually speaking) before "Enter the Dragon" came out cemented it; he was supposedly Shaolin in that movie.
4. Violence upon the body which led to the strengthening of the torso, arms, and legs, then the neck, head, abs, and even groin. In fact, some of the "72-Methods of Shaolin"¹⁵ are in practice today and do confer rather extreme examples of personal power.
5. Violence upon the brigands and evil outlaws. The victories in battle conferred fame, fortune (and disaster) upon the Shaolin Temple, and therefore Zen Buddhism in general, until the particular brand of Bodhidharma's Buddhism that was taught was spread, and morphed into modern styles and flavors, and has brought peace, hope, and perhaps frustration or misery (through which growth come) to over 500 million people (7% of the world)¹⁶!

The establishment of Karate, in America, was first from the soldiers in Okinawa and Japan after WWII, and then post-movie era (especially the 1960s, 1970s with Chuck Norris, etc.). One of those major movies ("Karate Kid") is **still producing jobs and discussion of the issue of human interactions and violence (related to male/female drama and intense rivalries**, via the show "Cobra Kai." The truth is that the issues brought up in that show are timeless. There is much that can be said in terms of the cycle of violence, and of the destruction of human society when things spin out of control (consider the finale of season 2!). But even more to the point, it's quite possible that because of the Law of Polarity, it will **always be this way for carbon-bio-organics**, which is what I suspect and suggest. There doesn't seem to be a lot of evidence of a pacifistic cumbaya anywhere on Earth, and perhaps even in the Universe. All the more to consider is this fact: the empowerment (in the show of kids!) of people is always mimsical, *even when those people sin/make mistakes*. Always mimsical. Karate has created so many jobs¹⁷, that it is easy to say it is a cinch as a MIMS

¹¹ https://www.academia.edu/77592483/MIMS_2_83_POS_Theory

¹² <https://terebess.hu/zen/huike.html>

¹³ https://www.goldenelixir.com/publications/eot_quanzhen.html

¹⁴ Shaolin monks: Wheel Of Life <http://www.shaolinwheeloflife.com/>

¹⁵ training-methods-72-arts-shaolin by Tanjin 1934.pdf

¹⁶ https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-27953-0_5

¹⁷ There are over 4,051 **karate** instructors **currently** employed in the **United States**. 33.0% of all **karate** instructors are women, while 67.0% are men. <https://www.zipppia.com/karate-instructor-jobs/demographics/>

based on that alone. Never mind that, in fact, teaching men (the greatest victims of violence), women (common victims of domestic violence) and children (one of the most vulnerable to violence) how to apply violence to push back upon the enemy, or “evil men” or “abusive people” will also act **instantly** as a MIMS. The fact is that karate, and all sorts of martial arts, boxing, sports, MMA, etc., teaches (for the most part) the ‘Miyagi’ style of self-discipline over top of *doing* the violence, so as to benefit the kids and people’s lives. In fact, for the most part, martial arts improves lives and is not involved in the lives of criminals. If criminals had self-discipline, usually they would not [usually] become criminals!

Hiroshima & Nagasaki

There is nothing mimsical about the nuclear bombs, themselves. When I was 18, in AP US History class I argued against the entire class, left, right, and center, against the dropping of the bomb. This is because of the new precedent set in war, the use of a ‘weapon of the gods’ by mankind, and meddling in affairs, and of course I knew the history of the spying and the Cold War.

Nevertheless, there is a fact about this event: it ended the war, ended the monarchy’s rule, ended imperialism in Japan (for now), and created “The Miracle.”¹⁸ This economic boom/upturn is not the only example of this effect. Vietnam, as well, has completely modernized since then and become incredibly robust for investment and industrialization, whereas it was stuck in a form of agricultural backwards morass - the same type that led China to be called “the sick man of Asia” in the 1800s. Frankly, it was behind even as recently as 1990, and now it is the 21st century (how’s that for the power of FRL!?).

That doesn’t excuse the atomic bombs, or the carpet/napalm bombing, or anything. It only means that the results of violence can, and frequently in history have been, to mimsically create peace, growth, and technological advancement. This happened after Ashoka the Great, Alexander the Great, Gengis Khan, and of course the American Revolution *and* the Marshall Plan in Europe. In fact, it seems such an indispensable fact that the elite and Military Industrial Complex have come to believe that if they can fake a scenario where the United States of America ® Empire can “be the hero” it will justify just about anything in the Middle East. Thus the Project for a New American Century¹⁹ of the neocons, and the endless “War on Terror” from the neolib. Etc. With the creation of ISIS and failure in Afghanistan and Iraq, we know this is, of course, wrong²⁰. The conditions which led to WWII cannot be easily faked, and they are, in fact, not desirable. Nor is all of the Marxist related death of the 20th Century, which only harms Human Momentum - from a SPACERS point of view.

Nevertheless: violence of the great type as we saw in Hiroshima and Nagasaki can act to lead to a long, peaceful period of growth and transition. That... is pretty messed up, but it is mirrored in how rivers and their rapids express the Tao. Alternating periods of flat and calm, with violent turbulence and deathly hallows and harrowing journeys.

The Tale of Unlikely Friends

The stories of boys who start as enemies, because one bullies the other (threatened by them, their niche, etc.), and then fight and become lifelong friends is a common trope. It’s in anything from “Karate Kid” (“Cobra Kai”) to “Rocky V”, “Stand By Me”, etc. These aren’t “Lord of the Flies” type scenarios, mind you, and

¹⁸ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Japanese_economic_miracle

¹⁹ <https://www.duo.uio.no/bitstream/handle/10852/25398/Ferdigxmasteroppgave.pdf>

²⁰ Of course this has led to the War Economy/”sustainable war.”

in fact that might be an anti-MIMS of a story. Usually in such tough times, people start to band together. Most writers and real-life stories wind up with a way. There are horror stories, like Hurricane Katrina... where lack of resources leads to relentless competition and murder, assault, rape, etc. But often, there is the opposite. It isn't cumbaya, but it is in fact cooperative. When a bully uses violence, and is given into, he/she bullies more. When the victim uses violence and they establish boundaries, suddenly the two people or two groups (think Rwanda) know one another, and they cease to hurt one another. If they don't do great things, at least they cease doing toxic things. Some people, as it happens, need to be insulted to show you respect. That's soft violence, but I suspect it comes from the same principle or equation subset in Causality. This should be used, instead of heavy-handedness and controllerism, by schools and churches to increase friendships. Sadly, because of the lies of pacifism and pacifists, the propaganda and misuse of "turn the other cheek" it isn't, and may not be through the entire gynocalization of the West. But the Asiatic societies, with their almost religious devotion to martial arts and war, and to the gods, continue to promote patriarchal systems, and have no problem implementing this system.

Domestic Violence

Oh no, I've strayed into the no-no-land. A million feminazis have 'cried out in pain' and anger, showing that their seething rage and REEEE is "stunning and brave." In point of fact, it isn't stunning and brave to not talk about the truth of DV, such as the fact that the greatest % of victims are men and children, almost all of it unreported. Why? Because our society puts up with violence from females, since they tend to cause less average damage. My friend temporarily lost custody of his kids and had done no violence, while his wife had shoved him to the ground repeatedly, and lied to the courts. She also emasculated him in church, with friends, etc. and while he went and got dry, she had no stipulations to get sober or off the weed. This is a common enough thing that now there is both a Men's Rights Activist (MRA) movement and a Men Going Their Own Way (MGTOW) movement. I support the former and not the latter, but I understand both personally.²¹

But what is the outcome of **actual**, factual DV? If there is no neglect, it's been my experience to see that the person grows into a strong, centered, humble and very conscientious person. This doesn't excuse DV in the least. But it doesn't seem that DV (except murder and mutilation) is what ruins people. It is neglect and resentment, casting and degrading that does it. DV is nothing compared to the emotional and verbal abuse -and I mean *real* verbal abuse not 'microaggressions', arguing at volume, and other claptrap of the feminine horde and twitterscape. DV doesn't break people, it challenges them, for a time. And like it or not, most victims of DV become incredibly spiritual people, good Christians, etc. They are forgiving, compassionate, tolerant folks with a "good head on their shoulders" instead of a "chip." The world is a rough place, and myself being a victim of it since age 3 when I was beaten up by black boys I thought were my friends, I can attest to one fact: the tougher you are, the better your chances for survival. Being jaded may suck, from an emotional standpoint. Angst is tough, and depression tougher. But what really hurts is being victimized time after time because you never understood violence thoroughly, or the minds of the evil and depraved, enough to get the violence in you to return it, if need be. A tough word, tough look, etc. and a propensity to bring trouble if it finds you is actually quite good, if you can manage it and not lose yourself to self-destruction like drugs, porn addiction, alcoholism, and criminality, etc.

²¹ https://www.academia.edu/40245389/Boxing_Out_Hyper_Masculinity

Summary

In conclusion I just want to emphasize that violence, as taught by God, is reserved, patient, and loving... but **extreme when needed**. The amount of energy used in God's Anger or Universal Violence is always far, far surpassing what we perceive as necessary. And that is on purpose. Most of the time (99.999%) we should be at peace, easygoing, and compliant. Much of the time we should be tolerant and a little of the time accepting. Always, we should have boundaries and values that we are worthy enough and demanding enough of ourselves to defend. But rarely, as Jesus showed with the moneylenders, should we resort to violence. However, it can, and has been many times a MIMS, and therefore people should cease to purport the anti-MIMS of pacifism which never gives the context or room for a person to defend themselves, as they should (and for many reasons). This is coming from a man that has been frequently maligned, lied about, and said to be violent but never has been (despite my extensive and very violent knowledge and belief set). I've never even taken revenge - which I always have believed in. But I urge people to consider their capabilities - of many sorts in survival and resilience - and most especially their physical, mental, and spiritual capacity for violence. Both taking and giving. Consider it: daily. For Nature and God's Universe is violent in every single moment.

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